

**SOPS FOR LANGUAGE SAMPLE COLLECTION
PROOF OF PRINCIPLE (POP) TRIAL**

**Version 1.4
15 October 2025**

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Summary of Changes
1.0	2025 August 24	N/A
1.1	2025 September 8	- SharePoint upload directions added
1.2	2025 September 9	- REDCap directions updated - SharePoint upload directions updated
1.3	2025 September 22	- Minor edits
1.4	2025 October 15	- Changes to recording procedure

GENERAL DIRECTIONS

COLLECTING LANGUAGE SAMPLES

Directions

Collect and record the PSYCHS and the NSI interviews at each timepoint for each participant using this SOP.

Generate and upload audio recordings for the PSYCHS and the NSI interviews at each time point using the directions described below.

Direct questions to zarina.bilgrami@emory.edu.

1. RECORDING LANGUAGE SAMPLES – ON SITE

1.1 Equipment and Preparation

Equipment needed

1 laptop computer

- You will use this as a recording device while conducting the interview in the same room. Video data does not need to be collected, so the camera may be off, but the computer should be positioned between you and the participant so that both voices are captured.

Zoom application installed (requirements will vary based on type of device – see Zoom download page for appropriate version: <https://zoom.us/download>).

- HIPAA-compliant Zoom accounts created through Yale University should always be used to create meeting links for audio recording of the PSYCHS and the NSI interviews

Preparation

It is best to email your participant the day prior to ensure they have these requirements met as well as a quiet place to sit that will minimize background noise and interruptions.

Before you start, you will want to change some items in your Recordings settings. This only needs to be completed on the interviewer's laptop.

1. Open the settings in your Zoom application by selecting your profile icon in the top right corner of the window and clicking **Settings**
2. Go to **Recordings** on the left-hand menu page and select a local folder on your encrypted machine where you would like recorded zoom files to be stored until you transfer them to SharePoint.

Local recording storage

When the subject has joined the Zoom call, you need to ensure you **BOTH** have changed some settings before you begin.

3. Once in settings, go to Audio on the left-hand menu page. Scroll down to **Audio profile** section.

- Select the box that says **Zoom background noise removal**
- Select **Auto (automatically adjusts noise suppression)** from pulldown menu

Audio profile

You will be recording the PSYCHS interviews and NSI interviews in succession on a single recording. You should not leave the Zoom call link between the interviews. Use the Pause Recording function when you need to stop the recording (i.e., a bathroom break during between PSYCHS and NSI); this will ensure that all the audio for each assessment stays in one file.

4. **Begin by recording the PSYCHS interview.** To record the interview, press the record button on the bottom of the screen and select **Record to this Computer**. First, please ensure your computer is encrypted.

5. During the interviews, if you need to interrupt the recording for any reason, press the **Pause Recording** button to ensure that Zoom generates only one video file for the interview.

1.2 Filling out the Run Sheet

You will be filling out a single run sheet for the PSYCHS interview and the NSI interview.

1. Navigate to the Yale REDCap and select the subject's **PSYCHS & NSI AV Recording Run Sheet**.
2. You will be asked to confirm whether the audio was recorded to a single file and uploaded to SharePoint.
3. At the end of the form you will be asked about questions about any protocol deviations and quality of the recording.

1.3 Naming Conventions and Data Transfer to SharePoint

Zoom will generate a folder with several files, only one of which will need to be uploaded to SharePoint. The name of this umbrella folder will be autogenerated and will include the date of the recording and the title you used during the call, amongst other information. It will appear in whichever path you designated your files to download in Section 1.1.

1. Inside the downloaded folder, you will find a video file and an audio-only file. **You will only be uploading the audio file to SharePoint.** An additional "Audio Record" subfolder may appear, but it is not required for this project.

2. **You will also complete a single SharePoint form for both PSYCHS and NSI recordings.**
 - a. If you were unable to record the PSYCHS and NSI in a single sitting (i.e., conducted it over two days), and there are multiple parts to one type of interview, you may associate multiple audio files with one SharePoint form. You will indicate this in the subject's REDCap form as well.

3. Access the SharePoint form through this link:
<https://share.teamforms.app/form/ZDMzODRjODctNDBkMS00ZTNmLTliNGEtYzlkMjVjNTJjMzNiOmRkOGNiZWJiLTlxMzktNGRmOC1iNDExLTRIM2U4N2FiZWl1YzpmZGM1ZTZiYi1hOWQ1LTQ5ZDUtYWQzYS05NzAwNWQ4NDVIN2I=>

4. Fill out the required fields on the SharePoint form and upload the appropriate audio files to the form. **Complete the following for the combined interview recordings:**
 - a. **Select your site**
 - b. **Confirm** that the corresponding visit **REDCap runsheet** has been filled out
 - c. **Enter AMPSCZ Subject ID**
 - d. **Select Visit ID** for time point in trial
 - e. **Select date of recording**
 - i. This date must match the Zoom file's date
 - ii. If the interview was recorded over two days, use the date from the first part of the recording
 - f. Upload files: you can drag and drop files or choose them from your local directory by clicking **“Browse”**

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `share.teamforms.app`. The page title is **ProCAN Audio Upload**. The form contains the following elements:

- File Upload** section header.
- ProCAN Site ***: A dropdown menu.
- Runsheet filled out in REDCap ***: A checkbox.
- AMPSCZ Subject ID ***: A text input field.
- Visit ID ***: A dropdown menu.
- Date of Audio Recording ***: A date picker field.
- Upload ***: A dashed box containing a cloud icon and the text "Drop files to attach, or [browse](#)".
- ** ONLY UPLOAD THE AUDIO FILE ****: A note below the upload area.
- Submit**: A blue button at the bottom left.
- Powered by **Team Forms**: Text at the bottom center.

2. RECORDING LANGUAGE SAMPLES – REMOTE

2.1 Equipment and Preparation

Equipment needed

2 laptop computers with front facing camera – one for the interviewer and one for the interviewee.

Zoom application installed (requirements will vary based on type of device – see Zoom download page for appropriate version: <https://zoom.us/download>).

- HIPAA-compliant Zoom accounts created through Yale University should always be used to create meeting links for audio recording of the PSYCHS and the NSI interviews

Preparation

It is best to email your participant the day prior to ensure that these requirements are met, as well as a quiet place to sit that will minimize background noise and interruptions.

Before you start, you will want to change some items in your Recordings settings. This only needs to be completed on the interviewer’s laptop.

1. Open the settings in your Zoom application by selecting your profile icon in the top right corner of the window and clicking **Settings**
2. Go to **Recordings** on the left-hand menu page and select a local folder on your encrypted machine where you would like recorded zoom files to be stored until you transfer them to SharePoint.

Local recording storage

When the subject has joined the Zoom call, you need to ensure you **BOTH** have changed some settings before you begin.

3. Once in the settings, go to Audio on the left-hand menu page. Scroll down to **Audio profile** section.

- Select the box that says **Zoom background noise removal**
- Select **Auto (automatically adjusts noise suppression)** from pulldown menu

Audio profile

You will be recording the PSYCHS interviews and NSI interviews in succession on a single recording. You should not leave the Zoom call link between the interviews. Use the Pause Recording function when you need to stop the recording (i.e., a bathroom break during between PSYCHS and NSI); this will ensure that all the audio for each assessment stays in one file.

4. **Begin by recording the PSYCHS interview.** To record the interview, press the record button on the bottom of the screen and select **Record to this Computer**. First, please ensure your computer is encrypted.

5. During the interviews, if you need to interrupt the recording for any reason, press the **Pause Recording** button to ensure that Zoom generates only one video file for the interview.

2.2 Filling out the Run Sheet

You will be filling out a single run sheet for the PSYCHS interview and the NSI interview.

1. Navigate to the Yale REDCap and select the subject's **PSYCHS & NSI AV Recording Run Sheet**.
2. You will be asked to confirm whether the audio was recorded to a single file and uploaded to SharePoint.
3. At the end of the form you will be asked about questions about any protocol deviations and quality of the recording.

2.3 Naming Conventions and Data Transfer to SharePoint

Zoom will generate a folder with several files that will need to be uploaded to SharePoint. The name of this umbrella folder will be autogenerated and will include the date of the recording and the title you used during the call, amongst other information. It will appear wherever you set your files to download in Section 1.1.

1. Inside the downloaded folder, you will find two video files and two audio-only files—one set for PSYCHS and one set for NSI. **You will only be uploading the audio files to SharePoint.** The files appear in the order they were recorded (e.g., if PSYCHS was recorded first, the first audio file will correspond to that session). An additional "Audio Record" subfolder may appear, but it is not required for this project.

2. **You will also complete a single SharePoint form for both PSYCHS and NSI recordings.**
 - a. If you were unable to record the PSYCHS and NSI in a single sitting (i.e., conducted it over two days), and there are multiple parts to one type of interview, you may associate multiple audio files with one SharePoint form. You will indicate this in the subject’s REDCap form as well.
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4. Fill out the required fields on the SharePoint form and upload the appropriate audio files to the form. **Complete the following for the combined interview recordings:**
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- Upload ***: A dashed box containing a cloud icon and the text "Drop files to attach, or [browse](#)".
- ** ONLY UPLOAD THE AUDIO FILE ****: A note below the upload area.
- Submit**: A blue button at the bottom left of the form.

At the bottom of the page, it says "Powered by [Team Forms](#)".